

IMPROVING METHODOLOGY FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13134340>

Abstract

This article is devoted to the issues of improving the methodology for organizing marketing activities of higher educational institutions. The paper examines the main problems that arise when implementing a marketing strategy in universities and suggests ways to solve them. Particular attention is paid to the need for an integrated approach to organizing marketing activities, including research of the educational services market, development of marketing programs, effective management of the university brand and interaction with target audiences. It is reviewed the world experience in organizing the marketing activities of higher educational institutions, and also proposed recommendations for optimizing the marketing activities of universities aimed at increasing their competitiveness.

Keywords: marketing of higher education, marketing activities of universities, university brand management, digital marketing, data-driven.

Introduction

Modern higher education institutions operate in conditions of high competition for attracting applicants, which determines the need for effective organization of marketing activities. Marketing in universities plays a key role in creating a favorable image, promoting educational services and building long-term relationships with target audiences. However, existing approaches to organizing marketing work in higher education institutions are often characterized by fragmentation and lack of consistency.

In this regard, the development of a perfect methodology for organizing the marketing activities of universities, which would ensure the complexity, consistency and effectiveness of implemented marketing activities, is of particular relevance. This article is aimed at solving this scientific and practical problem.

Theoretical foundations of organizing marketing activities in higher education.

Marketing activities of universities represent systematic work to study the market for educational services, generate demand for the offered educational programs, promote the brand of an educational organization and establish long-term mutually beneficial relationships with target audiences.

Authors F.Kotler and others emphasize the importance of universities using marketing approaches to

attract applicants and increase competitiveness¹. Researchers D.D.Dill, A.B.Lee analyze the specifics of using marketing tools in the field of higher education and focus on the need for a client-oriented approach². Author G.M.Ligutti examines the role of digital technologies in the marketing activities of universities and their impact on interaction with target audiences³. Authors I.M.Popova, S.V.Kochneva consider effective channels for promoting educational services of higher educational institutions⁴. Author L.L.Stasyuk explores the introduction of a client-oriented approach to university management⁵. R.E.Mansurov considers the development of an effective marketing strategy for the university⁶. Authors R.R.Salikhova, I.V.Degtyareva analyze the role of marketing communications in the management of a higher educational institution⁷. Author I.B.Romanova proposes the use of marketing tools to assess the effectiveness of a university⁸.

I.Berezin in his work says that the market for educational services is the material interaction of participants in the educational process: students, organizations providing educational services, individuals and organizations paying for these services⁹. M.A.Gavrilova defines the educational services market as a system of economic relations regarding the purchase and sale of educational services directly in demand by both

¹Котлер Ф., Фокс К.Ф. "Стратегический маркетинг для учебных заведений" (2007) (<https://www.williamspublishing.com/Books/978-5-8459-1145-8.html>)

²Дилл Д.Д., Ли А.Б. "Маркетинг в высшем образовании" (2009): Ссылка: <https://vo.hse.ru/2009--1/26589787.html>

³Лигутти Г.М. "Цифровой маркетинг в высшем образовании" (2019): <https://www.routledge.com/Digital-Marketing-for-Higher-Education/Ligutti/p/book/9781138673885>.

⁴Попова И.М., Кочнева С.В. "Маркетинговые коммуникации в продвижении образовательных услуг вуза" (2017), <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/marketingovye-kommunikatsii-v-prodvizhenii-obrazovatelnyh-uslug-vuza>.

⁵Стасюк Л.Л. "Маркетинговая ориентация высшего учебного заведения" (2012)https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321320895_Marketingovaa_orientacia_vysiego_ucebnogo_zavedenie.

⁶Мансуров Р.Е. "Маркетинговая стратегия развития университета" (2014) (<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/marketingovaya-strategiya-razvitiya-universiteta>)

⁷Салихова Р.Р., Дегтярева И.В. "Маркетинговые коммуникации в системе управления вузом" (2015) <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/marketingovye-kommunikatsii-v-sisteme-upravleniya-vuzom>

⁸Романова И.Б. "Маркетинговый подход к оценке эффективности деятельности вуза" (2016) (<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/marketingovyy-podhod-k-otsenke-effektivnosti-deyatelnosti-vuza>)

⁹Березин И.С. Крупнейшие потребительские рынки России. Объем, динамика, перспективы. – М.: Беловодье, 2010. – 272 с.

collective and individual consumers¹⁰.

1-picture. Key elements of the structure of marketing activities of higher educational institutions¹¹

It is important to note that these elements must be closely interconnected and implemented comprehensively within the framework of a unified marketing strategy of the university. This provides a synergistic effect and allows you to achieve your marketing goals with the greatest efficiency.

Methodology for organizing marketing activities in higher education

The proposed methodology for organizing marketing activities in higher education institutions includes the following main stages:

1. Strategic analysis of the external and internal environment of the university

At this stage, a comprehensive analysis of macro- and microenvironmental factors affecting the marketing activities of the university is carried out. The main trends in the development of the educational services market are studied, the key needs and preferences of target audiences are identified, and opportunities and threats to the university are assessed. There are also analyzed the internal resources and competencies of the organization that ensure the implementation of the marketing strategy.

2. Development of a university marketing strategy

Based on the results of the strategic analysis, a university marketing strategy is formed, including targets, priority market segments, positioning of educational services and the university brand, as well as key marketing initiatives. At the same time, the marketing strategy should be closely integrated with the development strategy of the university as a whole.

3. Development of a marketing communications package

At this stage, the optimal set of marketing communications tools is determined (advertising, public relations, digital marketing, personal selling, etc.) that contribute to the effective promotion of educational services and the university brand. Specific communication

The structure of marketing activities of higher education institutions includes the following key elements:

Managing relationships with consumers of educational services.

Formation and promotion of the university brand.

programs and activities are developed, agreed on timing, budget and expected results.

4. Organization of a customer relationship management system

An important component of the methodology is building a system for managing relationships with consumers of educational services (applicants, students, their parents, etc.). This includes segmenting target audiences, developing client programs, introducing CRM technologies, and organizing an effective feedback system.

5. Branding and reputation management

A significant element of the methodology is the formation and promotion of a strong university brand. This involves the development of a unique selling proposition, corporate identity, as well as systematic work to manage the reputation of an educational organization.

6. Monitoring and control of the effectiveness of marketing activities

The final stage includes the development of a system of key performance indicators for the university's marketing activities, organizing monitoring of the achievement of these indicators, as well as taking corrective measures if necessary.

Foreign experience of research work.

If we consider a review of global experience in improving the methodology for organizing marketing activities of higher education institutions by country, it can be noted that many leading universities around the world use diverse but comprehensive approaches to organizing marketing activities, adapting them to their unique conditions and goals.

Leading American universities actively use targeted digital marketing, including to attract international students. Branding and reputation management of universities are widely used to create a unique positioning. It is common practice to measure the return on investment (ROI) of marketing initiatives.

¹⁰ аврилова М.А. Непрерывное профессиональное педагогическое образование: проблемы, суждения, опыт работы // Научные исследования: информация, анализ, прогноз: коллективная монография / П.Ф. Кравчук, В.В. Попов, Н.И. Лыгина и др.; под общей ред. проф. О.И.

Кирикова. – Воронеж: Воронежский государственный педагогический университет, 2003. – Кн. 1. – С. 93-102.

¹¹ Подготовлено автором в ходе исследования.

British universities are focused on improving the customer experience of applicants and students at all stages of interaction. A data-driven approach to making marketing decisions based on deep data analysis is being actively implemented. Internationalization strategies, including attracting international students, are popular.

Australian universities pay great attention to segmenting their target audience and developing personalized marketing programs. Mobile marketing and integration with social media are widely used to communicate with applicants. Marketing initiatives aimed are common at engaging current students and alumni.

German universities actively take a holistic approach to branding, including visual identity and cultivating brand values. Considerable attention is paid to marketing research to understand the needs and preferences of the target audience. Partnerships with enterprises and foreign universities are being developed to strengthen positioning.

Singapore universities demonstrate best practices in using the latest digital technologies for marketing communications. Much attention is paid to internationalization, including attracting foreign students and developing global connections. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing efforts is used for their continuous improvement.

Analysis and result of the research.

The methodology discussed above will allow:

Form an integrated approach to organizing marketing activities, ensuring consistency and interconnection of individual elements.

Strengthen the focus of marketing programs on the needs and preferences of target audiences.

Increase the efficiency of promoting educational services and the brand of universities through the rational use of marketing tools.

Strengthen the loyalty and trust of consumers of educational services in universities by building long-term mutually beneficial relationships.

Increase the effectiveness of universities' marketing activities, which is reflected in an increase in the number of applicants, improved financial performance and strengthened competitive positions.

In addition, within the framework of a higher educational institution, it is necessary to operate a special service that should solve the following tasks:

- continuous improvement of the quality of existing educational services;
- analysis of the economic activities of an educational institution;
- quality management;
- development of the educational institution's advertising policy;
- conducting marketing research.

Thus, marketing of a higher education institution is a necessary and most important part of its activities. Today we can say with confidence that higher education institutions that do not pay due attention to marketing activities have found themselves or will soon find themselves at a disadvantage, which will affect their competitiveness in the educational services market.

Conclusion

Thus, the proposed methodology for organizing the marketing activities of higher educational institutions is a comprehensive and systematic approach that provides an effective solution to the problems of attracting and retaining consumers of educational services, creating a favorable image and developing the competitive advantages of universities. Its practical implementation contributes to effectiveness and allows us to recommend this methodology for widespread implementation in the practice of marketing management in the field of higher education.

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